

“Jaina relativism and relativity physics”

by Jayant Burde : A Review

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The book “Jaina relativism and relativity physics” by Jayant Burde is one of the pioneering work to find the basis of Jaina philosophy particularly *anekāntavāda* and *syādvāda* in the realm of modern science. He proposed the book by firmly pin pointing our misconception about the way general people relates jaina relativism with Einstein relativity of physics. Then he firmly establishes the connection of jaina relativism called *anekāntavāda* and *syādvāda* which are the main pillars of jaina philosophy and religion with the modern science like Einstein’s relativity, quantum theory, and uncertainty principle.

He divided the book in fourteen chapters and in each chapter he beautifully explains the various aspects of jaina philosophy in a lucid way by giving interesting examples and also explains the hard core theory of physics without using mathematics with the help of simple diagrams and examples keeping in mind the general readers.

In the introductory chapter he correctly explains the original meaning of ‘absolutism’ and ‘non-absolutism’ philosophy of *anekāntavāda* and *syādvāda* and then the concept of absoluteness in the realm of Einstein theory of special relativity.

Then a brief history of Jainism, the religion and the philosophy is given to understand a general people to feel the culture, socio economic

background of Jainism. The fundamental philosophy of Jainism like *ahimsā*, meaning of soul, *nirvāṇa* etc. is also beautifully explained.

In the third chapter what is meant by eternal mind and knowledge from the point of view of jaina philosophy is given in a very lucid way. The meaning of ‘identity’, ‘the law of contradiction’, and ‘the law of excluded’ in the context of *anekāntavāda* of jaina philosophy is well explained.

The Jains believes in non-absolutism, and how *anekāntavāda* a sevenfold prediction called *saptabhaṅgī*, gives a complete meaning of non-absolutism in reality is well explained by giving thoughtful examples for each sevenfold prediction in the fourth chapter. Here also the interpretation of the word *avaktavya* following the philosophy of *saptabhaṅgī* is given in a thoughtful way.

The doctrine of syadvada and *nayavāda* is discussed in the fifth chapter with some criticism of *syādvāda*. The seven points of *nayavada* is also well illustrated here.

The Jainism and Buddhism and their close relationship is discussed in the sixth chapter of this book. The similarities of *anekāntavāda* of Jainism and also their core difference i.e. buddhist’s quartet and jaina’s septet, are well mentioned in this chapter.

What kind of logic is the doctrine of *anekānta* or *syādvāda* of jaina’s philosophy, is beautifully explained in this book by taking reference of some eminent scholars. Whether it is justified or not to say *syādvāda* or *nayavada* as a many valued logic system is explained in great detail. To explain the philosophy of *saptabhaṅgī* by modal logic or conditional statement or model of existential quantifier by various researchers are also presented here. He also showed that *saptabhaṅgī* may be explained by pure mathematics of relational calculus in a very promising way.

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The journey of physics from Galilean relativity of physics to Einstein relativity of physics is discussed in chapter eight and nine. The foundation of Einstein special theory of relativity by gradually making the concept of electromagnetic waves, field, Newton's laws, and ether drag hypothesis for a lay man is done in a very simple way. He illustrates the hard core concepts of Einstein special theory of relativity such as time dialation, length contraction, minkowski's space-time, light cone, addition of velocity and Poincare motion by using some very simple diagrams in most convincing way. Then he develops the interrelationship of the philosophy of *anekāntavāda* with the Einstein special theory of relativity and also general theory of relativity. From the concept of modern science he undoubtedly established the philosophy of non-absolutism of jaina philosophy. The philosophy of non-absolutism is also seen in nature and established by modern science in the form of Heisenberg uncertainty principle, existence of elementary particles, virtual particles like neutrino etc.

At last he rightly said that the core philosophy of *anekanta* or *syādvāda*, by making a true philosophical analysis of *saptabhaṅgī* with some beautiful practical examples, is consistent with modern scientific thought. The main philosophy of Jainism, *ahimsā* is also very relevant in the recent socio economic status of the world in a multi-dimensional way.

JAIN BHAWAN : ITS AIMS AND OBJECTS

Since the establishment of the Jain Bhawan in 1945 in the Burra Bazar area of Calcutta by eminent members of Jain Community, the Jain Bhawan has kept the stream of Jain philosophy and religion flowing steadily in eastern India for the last over fiftyeight years. The objectives of this institution are the following:

1. To establish the greatness of Jainism in the world rationally and to spread its glory in the light of new knowledge.
2. To develop intellectual, moral and literary pursuits in the society.
3. To impart lessons on Jainism among the people of the country.
4. To encourage research on Jain Religion and Philosophy.

To achieve these goals, the Jain Bhawan runs the following programmes in various fields.

1. School:

To spread the light of education the Bhawan runs a school, the Jain Shikshalaya, which imparts education to students in accordance with the syllabi prescribed by the West Bengal Board. Moral education forms a necessary part of the curricula followed by the school. It has on its roll about 550 students and 25 teachers.

2. Vocational and Physical Classes:

Accepting the demands of the modern times and the need to equip the students to face the world suitably, it conducts vocational and physical activity classes. Classes on traditional crafts like tailoring, stitching and embroidery and other fine arts along with Judo, Karate and Yoga are run throughout the year, not just for its own students, but for outsiders as well. They are very popular amongst the ladies of Burra Bazar of Calcutta.

3. Library:

“Education and knowledge are at the core of all round the development of an individual. Hence the pursuit of these should be the sole aim of life”. Keeping this philosophy in mind a library was established on the premises of the Bhawan, with more than 10,000 books on Jainism, its literature and philosophy and about 3,000 rare manuscripts, the library is truly a treasure trove. A list of such books and manuscripts can be obtained from the library.

4. Periodicals and Journals:

To keep the members abreast of contemporary thinking in the field of religion the library subscribes to about 100 (one hundred) quarterly, monthly and weekly periodicals from different parts of the world. These can be issued to members interested in the study of Jainism.

5. Journals:

Realising that there is a need for reasearch on Jainism and that scholarly knowledge needs to be made public, the Bhawan in its role as a research institution brings out three periodicals: *Jain Journal* in English, *Titthayara* in Hindi and *Śramaṇa* in Bengali. In 37 years of its publication, the Jain Journal has carved out a *niche* for itself in the field and has received universal acclaim. The Bengali journal *Śramaṇa*, which is being published for thirty year, has become a prominent channel for the sbvgftr54pread of Jain philosophy in West Bengal. This is the only Journal in Bengali which deals exclusively with